

Using AI to Accelerate Early-Stage Drug Discovery

Warren Huang

December 2025

1 Abstract:

The drug discovery process is time consuming. It is difficult for scientists to manually test millions of molecules. With the integration of AI into the drug discovery pipeline, the process of hit identification could be sped up exponentially. In this study, multiple machine learning models were trained to classify molecules based on their ability to be absorbed into the human bloodstream. The Random Forest Classifier had the highest accuracy score of 94.83% and an AUROC score of 0.98. These results demonstrate that AI has the potential to accelerate the virtual screening process and assist scientists in finding drug-like molecules more effectively.

2 Background:

Today, drug exploration can take anywhere from 15 to 20 years for a potential compound to reach the market. It takes extensive costs to find a suitable drug and thorough evaluation to pass FDA approval. There are trillions of potential molecules, each with vastly different properties. Testing each one manually is expensive and time consuming and would severely limit innovation and discovery. However, with the rise of AI, we hope to be able to speed up this process by automatically screening compound databases in silico while scientists use more of their time to test compounds that show promise. Specifically, we focus on Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion also known as ADME. ADME is important because it predicts how the body will react to a drug, which determines its safety, efficiency, and usage.

3 Methods:

In this study, the dataset used was obtained from the human intestinal absorption dataset curated by Hou et al. [1], which reports experimentally measured oral absorption values for drug-like compounds. The dataset consists of

648 chemical compounds. Prior to modeling, the data were cleaned by removing constant features, samples containing missing values (NaNs), and 5-fold cross validation was performed with a standard 80/10/10 train, validation, and test set split. Five machine-learning models were evaluated for their ability to classify molecules which included the Random Forest Classifier, Decision Tree Classifier, K-nearest Neighbors, SVM Linear, and Logistic Regression. The Random Forest classifier achieved the strongest performance with an accuracy of 94.83% (Accuracy = $\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$) and an AUROC score of 98%. AUROC is calculated by finding the ROC curve for both the x-axis (TPR = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$) and y-axis (FPR = $\frac{FP}{FP+TN}$) and finding the area underneath the curve.

$$\text{AUROC} = \int_0^1 \text{TPR}(x) dx$$

Further improvements were achieved through SelectKBest (optimal at 35 features) that chooses the top k features that affect human intestinal absorption, oversampling using SMOTE, and model tuning. Most of these methods increased predictive performance, with the exception of Grid Search CV that searches through all the possible combinations of hyperparameters to find the combination that yields the best model, which unexpectedly lowered accuracy.

Figure 1: Random Forest Classifier

4 Random Forest Classifier:

The Random Forest classifier is composed of many decision tree classifiers. Each tree is trained on a randomly selected subset of the training data and considers only a random subset of features when making splits. During prediction,

each tree outputs a class label, and the forest produces the final prediction by majority voting. Random Forests perform well because they reduce overfitting, are robust to noise, and can model complex interactions between features. Since the trees are trained independently, the effect of any single poorly performing or overfitted tree is minimized, as the final prediction is determined by the majority vote of all trees.

5 Results:

Figure 2 shows the confusion matrix for my model. There are many more True Positives and True Negatives with 146 and 17 respectively and relatively small False Positives and False Negatives of only 3 and 8 respectively. This demonstrates that the model accurately identifies potential hit molecules and rarely mislabels them. Furthermore, we can see from Figure 3 that there are more positive molecules that can be absorbed by the body. However, I used SMOTE which removes this data imbalance. This is just one small step toward using AI to help drug discovery, there are still many more improvements and optimizations that this model could go through. As AI becomes more and more advanced, it will help scientists in all different types of fields make breakthroughs.

Figure 2: The confusion matrix for the Random Forest Classifier. Adapted from [2].

Figure 3: The data set before and after applying SMOTE

6 Conclusion:

This project demonstrates that machine learning models such as Random Forest Classifiers have the potential to effectively identify potential drug-like molecules. Although the scope of this project is limited, we highlight how AI can accelerate the early-stages of drug discovery by screening molecules faster than traditional wet-lab methods. Future work includes training and evaluation on more diverse datasets, applying additional feature selection methods, and implementing complex deep learning algorithms such as message passing neural networks (MPNN) to improve performance. Ultimately, continued improvement in AI will aid in accelerating the drug discovery pipeline, the time it takes for a drug to hit the market, and, in the end, improve global health.

7 Acknowledgments:

I would like to thank my research advisor, Prof. Yan Liu and PhD student supervisor, Emily Nguyen from the University of Southern California, for helping me learn machine learning methods and their overall guidance.

References

- [1] Tingjun Hou, Junmei Wang, Wei Zhang, and Xiaojie Xu. Adme evaluation in drug discovery. 7. prediction of oral absorption by correlation and classification. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 2007.
- [2] Janosh. Illustrating the random forest algorithm in tikz. <https://tex.stackexchange.com/questions/503883/illustrating-the-random-forest-algorithm-in-tikz>, 2019. TeX StackExchange, CC BY-SA 4.0.